

Synthesis and Bioactive Nature of some New Bis(2-pyrazolin-3-yl)benzenes. Part-II

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Manuscript received 10 April 1990, revised 19 October 1990, accepted 23 April 1991

Cycloaddition of diazomethane to 3,3'-(1,3- and 1,4-phenylene)bis(1-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (3) at -20° in presence of triethylamine gave the title compounds (4). Their *N*-substituted derivatives (5-7) have been obtained by nitrosation, benzylation and benzenesulphonylation. The compounds 4 have been screened for antimicrobial and insecticidal activities.

THE study on pyrazolines has assumed importance in the recent past because of their bioactive nature^{1,2}. In our pursuit to probe further into the physiological activity, we report here the synthesis of some more new bis(2-pyrazolin-3-yl)benzenes. Thus, 3,3'-(1,3- and 1,4-phenylene)bis(1-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) have been used as substrates to obtain 4,4'-*m*- and *p*-phenylenebis(3-aryl-2-pyrazolines) by the cycloaddition of diazomethane in presence of a base, triethylamine (Scheme 1, Table 1).

Cycloaddition of diazomethane to Michael acceptors was reported³ to give both 1- and 2-pyrazolines depending upon the carbon atom of diazomethane attaches itself to α - or β -carbon atom of the double bond. The ambiguity about the formation of pyrazolines in such reaction systems was clarified recently⁴. Thus the recent reports confirm that 2-pyrazolines were the products of cycloaddition of diazomethane to conjugated olefins^{1,4-8}.

Further, in order to confirm the formation of 2-pyrazolines their *N*-substituted derivatives have been prepared by nitrosation, benzylation and benzenesulphonylation (Scheme 1, Table 1). Their structures were established by ir, nmr and mass spectral data. Compounds 4 showed ir bands at 3420-3350 (NH). Compounds 4-7 exhibited medium to strong bands at 1700-1660 cm^{-1} (C=O)⁹. However, compounds 5 displayed bands at 1510-1500 cm^{-1} for N=O^{1,4}, while 7 showed bands at 1305-1295 and 1150-1135 cm^{-1} for SO₂ group^{1,4}.

Pmr spectra of compounds 4-7 displayed an ABX pattern for the pyrazoline ring protons^{4-6,8-10}. The methylene and methine protons of 5-7 appeared slightly at downfield region (δ 4.08-4.30 and 4.38-4.62) in comparison to that of 4 (δ 3.42-3.70 and 3.82-4.20). A broad singlet which appeared for NH of 4 at δ 6.52-6.62 was absent in the spectra

- 4a) R - C₆H₄COCH=CH- is 1,3 and
R = (1) H, (2) 4-CH₃, (3) 4-CH₃O, (4) 4-Cl,
5) 4-Br, 6) 2,4-(CH₃O)₂
- b) R - C₆H₄COCH=CH- is 1,4 and
R = (1) H, (2) 4-CH₃, (3) 4-CH₃O, (4) 4-C₂H₅O,
5) 4-Br, (6) 2,4-(CH₃O)₂
- 5; Y=NO in (a) 3; and (b) 1
6; Z=C₆H₅CO in (a) 3; and (b) 1
7; Z=C₆H₅SO₂ in (a) 1; and (b) 1

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-7*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M. p. °C	Mol. formula (Mol. wt.)	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}	δ (ppm)
4a-1	71	137-38	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (423)	3 380 (NH), 1 665 (C=O)	3.48 (4H, d, methylene), 3.95 (2H, t, methine), 6.56 (2H, s, NH), 7.06-8.20 (13H, m, ArH)
2	70	123-24	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (451)	3 400 (NH), 1 685 (C=O)	2.27 (6H, s, methyl), 3.52 (4H, d, methylene), 4.10 (2H, t, methine), 6.61 (2H, s, NH), 7.12-8.26 (11H, m, ArH)
3	70	109-10	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (483)	3 380 (NH), 1 685 (C=O)	3.77 (6H, s, OCH_3), 3.58 (4H, d, methylene), 4.10 (2H, t, methine), 6.56 (2H, s, NH), 7.14-8.30 (11H, m, ArH)
4	66	97-98	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (491)	3 400 (NH), 1 685 (C=O)	3.60 (4H, d, methylene), 3.98 (2H, t, methine), 6.62 (2H, s, NH), 7.20-8.16 (11H, m, ArH)
5	72	112-13	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (580)	3 380 (NH), 1 680 (C=O)	3.62 (4H, d, methylene), 4.20 (2H, t, methine), 6.58 (2H, s, NH), 7.14-8.26 (11H, m, ArH)
6	76	93-94	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ (543)	3 420 (NH), 1 690 (C=O)	3.80 (12H, s, OCH_3), 3.48 (4H, d, methylene), 4.12 (2H, t, methine), 6.60 (2H, s, NH), 7.15-8.15 (9H, m, ArH)
4b-1	80	134-35	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (423)	3 360 (NH), 1 660 (C=O)	3.58 (4H, d, methylene), 3.92 (2H, t, methine), 6.56 (2H, s, NH), 7.04-8.18 (13H, m, ArH)
2	75	190-91	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (451)	3 380 (NH), 1 670 (C=O)	2.27 (6H, s, CH_3), 3.68 (4H, d, methylene), 3.98 (2H, t, methine), 6.58 (2H, s, NH), 7.15-8.06 (11H, m, ArH)
3	78	166-67	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (483)	3 360 (NH), 1 675 (C=O)	3.77 (6H, s, OCH_3), 3.60 (4H, d, methylene), 4.12 (2H, t, methine), 6.60 (2H, s, NH), 7.20-8.76 (11H, m, ArH)
4	69	120-22	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (511)	3 370 (NH), 1 670 (C=O)	1.44 (6H, t, OCH_2 , CH_3), 4.15 (4H, q, OCH_2 , CH_3), 3.58 (4H, d, methylene), 4.18 (2H, t, methine), 6.62 (2H, s, NH), 7.15-8.06 (11H, m, ArH)
5	67	151-52	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ (580)	3 350 (NH), 1 660 (C=O)	3.50 (4H, d, methylene), 3.98 (2H, t, methine), 6.62 (2H, s, NH), 7.20-8.26 (11H, m, ArH)
6	71	107-08	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ (543)	3 375 (NH), 1 685 (C=O)	3.80 (12H, s, OCH_3), 3.62 (4H, d, methylene), 4.12 (2H, t, methine), 6.61 (2H, s, NH), 7.15-8.20 (9H, m, ArH)
5a-3	51	106-07	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$ (540)	1 680 (C=O), 1 510 (N=O)	3.77 (6H, s, OCH_3), 4.18 (4H, d, methylene), 4.50 (2H, t, methine), 7.20-8.20 (11H, m, ArH)
5b-1	62	123-24	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$ (480)	1 660 (C=O), 1 500 (N=O)	4.20 (4H, d, methylene), 4.45 (2H, t, methine), 7.16-8.24 (13H, m, ArH)
6a-3	63	145-45	$\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ (690)	1 685 (C=O)	3.78 (6H, s, OCH_3), 4.15 (4H, d, methylene), 4.56 (2H, t, methine), 7.20-8.30 (11H, m, ArH)
6b-1	71	139-40	$\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (631)	1 660 (C=O)	4.12 (4H, d, methylene), 4.50 (2H, t, methine), 7.15-8.28 (13H, m, ArH)
7a-1	64	166-67	$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{30}\text{S}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ (702)	1 665 (C=O), 1 305, 1 135 (SO_2)	4.20 (4H, d, methylene), 4.60 (2H, t, methine), 7.12-8.34 (13H, m, ArH)
7b-1	66	138-39	$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{30}\text{S}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ (702)	1 660 (C=O), 1 300, 1 150 (SO_2)	4.28 (4H, d, methylene), 4.62 (2H, t, methine), 7.15-8.26 (13H, m, ArH)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

of 5-7. However, the singlet disappeared when the sample was treated with deuterium oxide.

The mass spectra of 4 showed molecular ion peak with low intensity at 40 eV corresponding to their molecular composition. The α -cleavage and pyrazoline ring cleavage appear to dominate in the disintegration of this molecule. The most predominant ion observed in this spectrum was benzoyl cation at m/z 105 with 100% intensity. This ion is not only derived from $M^{+\cdot}$ ion but also from different fragments by α -cleavage process. The forma-

tion of $(M-N_2)^{+\cdot}$, $(M-2N_2)^{+\cdot}$, azirine radical cation and cyclopropyl cations from the molecular ion may be due to pyrazoline ring cleavage process (Table 2). The appearance of bis(cyclopropyl) radical cation by the loss of two N_2 molecules from the $M^{+\cdot}$ ion indicates the presence of two pyrazoline moieties in the parent compound. The appearance of benzoyl cation, 1,3- and 1,4-bis-(vinyl)benzene radical cation and other prominent fragments justify the structure of parent compound.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL IONS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	M ⁺	[M-N ₂] ⁺	[M-C ₆ H ₅ NO] ⁺	[M-C ₆ H ₅ N ₂ O] ⁺	[M-C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O] ⁺	[C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O] ⁺	[M-C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂] ⁺	[C ₁₀ H ₈ O] ⁺	[C ₈ H ₆ NO] ⁺	[C ₁₀ H ₁₀] ⁺	[C ₇ H ₆ O] ⁺	[C ₆ H ₆] [±]
4a-1	422(4)	366(7)	291(10)	276(18)	221(8)	173(7)	160(7)	145(19)	132(16)	130(21)	105(100)	77(47)
4b-1	422(5)	366(8)	291(12)	276(27)	221(11)	173(8)	160(10)	145(22)	132(29)	130(22)	105(100)	77(44)

Antibacterial activity: The compounds 4 have been screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* following the reported method¹¹ at concentration of 10 µg ml⁻¹. None of them showed any bacterial activity.

Antifungal activity: The reported procedure¹² was followed using fungi *Curvularia lunata*, *Fusarium*

solani and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. The test compounds at concentrations 2:0, 500, 1000 µg ml⁻¹ were used. All these compounds effectively inhibited the spore germination of the fungi at higher concentration (Table 3). The compounds have a relatively lesser inhibitory effect over *H. oryzae* than *C. lunata* and *F. solani*. It is of significance to note that the antifungal activity and mode of action of these compounds varies depending upon the nature and position of the substituent in phenyl moiety.

Insecticidal activity: The mosquitoes of the species *Culex quinquefasciatus* have been used. The mortality on its larvae was recorded at intervals of 24, 48, 72 and 96 h. The results (Table 4) reveal that the activity increased progressively during 24 and 48 h, while there was no activity after 72 h.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Beckmann 18-A spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDC)₆; 60 MHz) on a Varian T-60 spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard, and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 instrument (40 and 70 eV; trap current: 100 µA) at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Silica gel-H (B.D.H.) was used for column chromatography.

Cycloaddition of diazomethane to 3: An ethereal solution of diazomethane^{13,14} (80 ml, 0.4 mol) and triethylamine (0.12 g) was added to a solution of 3¹⁵ (3.65 g, 10 mmol) in chloroform at 0°. The reaction mixture was maintained at -20° for 48 h. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded an yellow coloured product which on column chromatography (hexane-ether, 2:3) gave 4 (Table 1).

Nitrosation of 4: A well-cooled solution of 4 (10 mmol) in 1:1 hydrochloric acid (16 ml) was treated with a cold concentrated solution of sodium nitrite. The reaction mixture was cooled in an

TABLE 3—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	Concn. µg/ml ⁻¹	Inhibition %*		
		<i>C.l</i>	<i>F.s</i>	<i>H.o</i>
4a-1	250	58.4	42.5	20.7
	500	80.5	70.6	35.0
	1000	100.0	100.0	65.0
2	250	38.0	53.5	22.4
	500	67.5	67.5	43.2
	1000	100.0	100.0	85.0
3	250	62.0	37.2	23.2
	500	80.0	76.0	42.5
	1000	100.0	100.0	70.3
4	250	38.0	52.5	21.3
	500	68.7	86.5	49.1
	1000	90.0	100.0	60.0
5	250	45.0	40.0	16.7
	500	75.2	68.4	30.3
	1000	100.0	100.0	50.0
6	250	58.5	40.5	35.8
	500	82.3	80.4	72.5
	1000	100.0	100.0	90.5
4b-1	250	60.6	33.5	33.2
	500	74.5	70.2	40.4
	1000	100.0	100.0	80.0
2	250	53.4	40.2	38.4
	500	74.5	60.5	6.3
	1000	100.0	100.0	100.0
3	250	33.4	50.3	34.5
	500	64.6	100.0	53.4
	1000	100.0	100.0	90.2
4	250	65.5	34.5	28.5
	500	80.9	75.3	48.0
	1000	100.0	100.0	100.0
5	250	30.2	22.3	26.5
	500	76.6	68.5	43.4
	1000	100.0	100.0	65.0
6	250	43.5	36.3	39.3
	500	100.0	80.5	84.2
	1000	100.0	100.0	100.0

* *C.l*=*C. lunata*; *F.s*=*F. solani*; *H.o*=*H. oryzae*.

TABLE 4—LARVAL MORTALITY AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd. no.	Duration of exposure h	1 ppm		2 ppm		4 ppm	
		% Kill	Probit of kill	% Kill	Probit of kill	% Kill	Probit of kill
4a-1	24	14.80	3.96	18.37	4.98	19.20	4.12
	48	7.89	3.59	7.32	3.52	9.37	3.66
	72	—	—	—	—	—	—
	96	—	—	—	—	—	—
4b-1	24	7.65	3.52	4.08	3.25	4.59	3.36
	48	17.30	4.05	1.08	6.49	3.45	—
	72	7.27	3.52	—	—	—	—
	96	—	—	—	—	—	—

* % Kill is corrected using Abbott's formula for mortality in controls; (—)=no mortality.

ice-bath for 40–55 min. The solid that separated was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Benzoylation or benzenesulphonylation of 4: A solution of 4 (10 mmol) in pyridine (10 ml) was treated with benzoyl chloride or benzenesulphonyl chloride (20 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h. The contents were then cooled and poured in ice-cold dilute HCl. The resulting solid (6 or 7) was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T.S.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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